

A Consultation System for Statistical Analysis of Data

J.C. Dumer III T.P. Hanratty M.S. Taylor

US Army Ballistic Research Laboratory
Aberdeen Proving Ground, MD 21005-5066

ABSTRACT

Nonpare, a consultation system for analysis of data using nonparametric statistical procedures, is under active development. It is intended to serve as an intelligent interface that will act as a guide, an instructor, and an interpreter to a body of statistical software. Nonpare exists as a prototype, with a limited release planned in 1989 for field testing.

Introduction

Statistical software packages, to large extent, accept any properly configured data set and proceed to process it. Few if any checks are made to ensure the adequacy of the data and the suitability of the analysis, and little is done to provide an explanation or interpretation of the results. This requires a great deal from the user. Declining computation costs, together with increased availability of computers and proliferation of statistical software, has further enhanced the opportunity for faulty data analysis. Application of expert system techniques from artificial intelligence to produce more cognizant software is one approach to reversing this unfortunate trend.

Attempts to apply constructs from artificial intelligence to statistical analysis is in its infancy. Gale[1] has the most complete centrally-located account of research to date, although Hand, [2], [3], [4] is a prolific expositor in this area, and articles are beginning to make their appearance in the journals.

This paper details an effort at the US Army Ballistic Research Laboratory (BRL) to develop a consultation system for analysis of data using nonparametric statistical procedures. The system, called Nonpare, is intended to serve as an intelligent interface that will act as a guide, an instructor, and an interpreter to a body of statistical software. The system is currently a prototype, with a first release planned for 1989 for field testing.

Nonpare

Nonparametric procedures are characterized chiefly by the absence of restrictive distribution assumptions—notably freedom from dependence on the normal (Gaussian) distribution. Many nonparametric statistical procedures are exact rather than approximate for small data sets, and they

are the only confirmatory procedures which can be used to analyze data collected on a nominal or an ordinal scale of measurement. These procedures find use in a wide variety of disciplines and form the basis for texts by Conover, [5] Hollander and Wolfe, [6] Hettmansperger, [7] Lehmann, [8] and others.

Nonpare uses Genie, an expert system shell developed at the BRL, [9] to provide a frame-based production system with forward and backward inferencing as well as an explanation facility that allows the user to interrogate the system—what hypotheses are being entertained, what rules are being verified, what facts are in evidence. Genie was chosen over commercial expert system shells for the research and development of Nonpare in part because of its accessibility for modification.

Nonpare, shown schematically in figure 1, consists of three subsystems in addition to Genie.

Fig. 1. Nonpare system architecture.

The system dictionary is a facility whose purpose is to provide on-line explanation of statistical jargon that may appear during the interactive dialog between Nonpare and the user. Expert domain knowledge, codified in English-like rules, resides in the knowledge base. Once an appropriate procedure(s) has been identified, the data are analyzed and the results explained by the nonparametric data analysis component. Graphics is used to summarize the data and enhance the explanation. In total, the user is led within system limitations to an appropriate statistical procedure through an interactive process in which the user is

questioned and can in turn question the consultation system. Nonpare currently contains nineteen data analysis procedures. It is written in Interlisp-D and runs on Xerox 1100 Series Lisp machines.

An Illustrative Session

A detailed session with Nonpare follows, in which the main system features are illustrated. Any statistical procedure is a potential starting point, as in this session, the dialog of which begins in figure 2. The conventions that boldface denotes system prompts and brackets contain user response will be adopted. An occasional system response may be italicized but should not be confusing within the context of its appearance.

Example.

Suppose that a ballisticsian needs to assess the effectiveness of a newly designed kinetic energy penetrator against a specific armor plate. In particular, the experimenter would like to establish whether the probability of perforation exceeds .80, a level already attained with existing technology. Fourteen rounds are fired, and (p)erforation and (n)onperforation recorded to obtain: n, p, p, p, n, p, p, p, p, n, p, p, p, p. Is the $\Pr\{\text{perforation}\} > .80$?

```
Do you have a sample  $X_1, \dots, X_n$ ? y
Are you interested in whether the data conform to a specified
distribution? n
Are you interested in the probability of occurrence of a particular
category or event? y
Enter the name of the category of interest -> perforation
Are the n trials producing the values  $X_1, \dots, X_n$  independent?  $\lambda$ 
```

Fig. 2. Beginning dialog with Nonpare.

The session begins with a question about the configuration of the data.

Do you have a sample X_1, \dots, X_n ? The data, n, ..., p, look like X_1, \dots, X_n ; respond [y]es.

Are you interested in whether the data conform to a specified distribution ? Nonpare is investigating a possible goodness-of-fit situation. The user can establish this by asking [why], whereupon the inference engine supplies the rule under consideration. A nonstatistician, for whom this portion of the system is designed, and who is interested in whether $\Pr\{\text{perforation}\} > .80$, should respond [n]o, as indicated.

Are you interested in the probability of occurrence of a particular category or event ? [y]es. The user is interested in the probability of occurrence of a perforation.

Enter the name of the category of interest. [perforation]. Domain-dependent terminology is being introduced.

Are the n trials producing the values X_1, \dots, X_n independent ? Suppose the user is unsure of the technical implications of the term "independent." An acceptable response [What is independent] calls the system dictionary – as shown in figure 3.

```
Are the n trials producing the values  $X_1, \dots, X_n$  independent? what is in
dependent
Independence relates to freedom from external influence or control- here,
the reference is to measurements (data) being free to assume values
without regard to other measurements that may be made.
Are the n trials producing the values  $X_1, \dots, X_n$  independent? y
Does each trial have the same probability p of producing the perforation
? y
Are you interested in considering whether the probability of occurrence
of the perforation equals or is bounded by some specified value  $p^*$ ?  $\lambda$ 
```

Fig. 3. A call to the system dictionary.

Independence relates to freedom from external influence or control- here, the reference is to measurements (data) being free to assume values without regard to other measurements that may be made.

It may be impossible to rigorously define a term without reliance upon other terms that are equally obscure to a user with only a modest statistical background. This is the case here, where independence is bound to basic concepts of probability theory. Nonpare's response conveys the notion, but not the substance, of independence. Designing a system that can adjust to a user's level of knowledge remains a core problem in this area.

Are the n trials producing the values X_1, \dots, X_n independent ? [y]es.

Does each trial have the same probability p of producing the perforation ? [y]es. Notice that Nonpare is now using language the user provided, when it talks about probability of perforation.

Are you interested in considering whether the probability of occurrence of the perforation equals or is bounded by some specified value p^* ? [y]es. The user is interested in the inequality $\Pr\{\text{perforation}\} > .80$. After a [y]es response, the system suggests a possible approach, shown in figure 4.

```
The binomial test is an appropriate procedure. To execute the
binomial test, use the menu to complete this statement:
I am interested in testing the null hypothesis that: The probability
of occurrence of the perforation
Please enter:
equals some value p*
does not exceed p*
is at least p*
```

Fig. 4. A call to the nonparametric data analysis subsystem.

The menu allows the user to select either a two-sided or one-sided test of hypothesis and is a potential source of error. Nonstatisticians, not realizing that a null (or empty) hypothesis is chosen to be rejected, might mistakenly choose **is at least p^*** at this juncture. Again, *some* level of statistical competence is required. Selecting the hypothesis **does not exceed p^*** from the menu, the user obtains for confirmation (figure 5) the statement:

I am interested in testing the null hypothesis that: *The probability of occurrence of the perforation does not exceed p^* .*

```
I am interested in testing the null hypothesis that: The probability of
occurrence of the perforation does not exceed p*

Specify the sample size n -> 14
Specify a value for p* -> .80
Specify the number of datum values assigned to the perforation -> 11
```

Fig. 5. Hypothesis confirmation and parameter declaration.

Specify the sample size n. [14]

Specify a value for p^* . [.80]

Specify the number of datum values assigned to the perforation. [11]

The first two "Specify ..." commands determine the appropriate binomial distribution; the third determines the size of the critical region for the statistical procedure, which is explained in figure 7, following the system-generated histogram shown in figure 6.

Fig. 6. Statistical graph summary.

The histogram displays the probability of observing exactly $0 \leq n \leq 14$ armor perforations in fourteen shots if the true (but unknown) $\text{Pr}\{\text{perforation}\} = .80$. A statistician will readily assimilate this graph. If the user merely looks at it as a plot involving n rounds in which the light gray region, corresponding to $n \geq 11$, holds some special significance, and it provides some reassurance regarding the unseen computations, it will have served its purpose. Figure 7, which appears on the terminal simultaneously, explains that

The critical level of this test, corresponding to the light gray region, is .69

This means that if you reject the hypothesis (*The probability of occurrence of the perforation does not exceed .8*) you do so with a .69 probability of being in error.

```
The critical level of this test, corresponding to the light gray region,
is .69

This means that if you reject the hypothesis (The probability of
occurrence of the perforation does not exceed .8) you do so with a .69
probability of being in error.

Would you like to run the binomial procedure again? (y)
```

Fig. 7. Explanation and interpretation of results.

Since the investigation began with the assumption (null hypothesis) that the $\text{Pr}\{\text{perforation}\} \leq .80$, the evidence collected—eleven perforations, three nonperforations—is not sufficient to support abandonment of that assumption. A probability of being in error of .69 is more than a reasonable person would be willing to assume. And so, the response to the original question, Is the $\text{Pr}\{\text{perforation}\} > .80$? is a qualified no, the qualification being expressed through invocation of the critical level.

Would you like to run the binomial procedure again ?

A response of [y]es allows the user to exercise the binomial procedure directly, without having to re-enter the rule base. This is an excellent place to use Nonpare's tutorial capabilities to study the sensitivity of the binomial procedure to modification of parameter values or slight changes in the data.

Are you interested in determining an interval in which the probability p of occurrence of the perforation lies?

The foregoing analysis suggests that an assertion that the probability of perforation lies in the interval $(.80, 1]$ cannot realistically be made. What interval might be expected to capture this unknown parameter? A response of [y]es causes this question to be answered, first graphically, as in figure 8, and then verbally, as in figure 9.

Fig. 8. Display for a 95% confidence interval.

Figure 8 shows that the $\text{Pr}\{\text{perforation}\}$, whose estimate based on the fourteen firings is $\hat{p} = .78$, lies within the interval $[.48, .94]$ with a high level of confidence. This interval is so broad one can see why the assertion that $\text{Pr}\{\text{perforation}\} > .80$ is ill-advised. The formal

interpretation of the confidence interval is given as

The probability of occurrence of the perforation is contained in the interval [.48, .94] with an a priori probability .95 .

Are you interested in determining an interval in which the probability p of occurrence of the perforation lies? y

The probability of occurrence of the perforation is contained in the interval [.48, .94] with an a priori probability .95.

Would you like a confidence level other than .95 ? n

Fig. 9. Explanation and interpretation of the CI.

Would you like a confidence level other than .95 ? [no]. The 95% confidence level was prechosen. A [y]es response allows the user to control the confidence level. The session is terminated with a [n]o response, shown in figure 9.

At the conclusion of the session the inference engine displays a fact solution tree for all the intermediate decisions leading to the final conclusion. Buttoning with a mouse any node of the fact tree produces the logic leading to that location. These are features of the inference engine rather than Nonpare, but they are valuable as diagnostics to the developer and provide some measure of reassurance to the user.

Conclusions

We have established the feasibility of Nonpare to become a fully operational system. The essence of Nonpare is the rule based interface to accompanying software and the interpretation of the ensuing computations. Substantial work remains to be done: The amalgamation of knowledge supplied by the user and knowledge that may be extracted from the data, accomodation of uncertainty of response, and provision to modify responses, to name only a few. These obstacles however are surmountable, and growing interest in this area bodes well for the development and utility of systems of this type.

References

- [1] W.A. Gale, Ed., *Artificial Intelligence and Statistics* (Addison-Wesley, 1986).
- [2] D.J. Hand, Statistical expert systems: Necessary attributes, *J. Applied Statistics* (1985).
- [3] D.J. Hand, Expert systems in statistics, *Knowledge Engineering Review* (1986).
- [4] D.J. Hand, A statistical knowledge enhancement system, *JRSS* (1987).
- [5] W.J. Conover, *Practical Nonparametric Statistics* (John Wiley, 1980).
- [6] M. Hollander and D.A. Wolfe, *Nonparametric Statistical Methods* (John Wiley, 1973).
- [7] T.P. Hettmansperger, *Statistical Inference Based on Ranks* (John Wiley, 1984).
- [8] E.L. Lehmann, *Nonparametrics* (Holden-Day, 1975).
- [9] F.S. Brundick, et.al., Genie: An inference engine with applications to vulnerability analysis, Technical Report BRL-TR-2739, US Army Ballistic Research Laboratory, Aberdeen Proving Ground, MD (1986).